

Review

Corporate social responsibility of bank : The gaps

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Abstract: As a result of the widespread use of public funds by nations throughout the world in an effort to mitigate the effects of the global financial crisis that began in 2008, the level of public debt in many of these nations has reached unsustainable proportions. As a result of the downturn in the real economy, various nations were confronted with high unemployment rates and economic setbacks, both of which remain unsolved to this day. After the financial crisis, many people were concerned about how to rebuild faith in financial institutions and how banks may better contribute to socially responsible and economically sound growth. This article examines corporate social responsibility, also known as CSR, which is a mentality that places an emphasis on ethical standards. The CSR pyramid delineates distinct tiers of responsibility for corporate social responsibility. Taking responsibility for one's company's financial situation is the first step, as this is the basis upon which the pyramid is built; however, businesses must also adhere to the rules and regulations that have been established. The requirement to act justly and morally at all times is what we mean when we talk about having ethical responsibility. After the crisis, the responsibility for ensuring continued financial stability was passed on to the central banks of several nations. In order to accomplish this goal, central banks have established their very own policies for corporate social responsibility. Research is done on this practice from the perspective of how corporate social responsibility (CSR) might contribute to financial security.

Keywords: CSR, Corporate Social Responsibility, Bank

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Introduction

This section presents a review of the existing relevant theoretical and empirical literature to the study proposed. The goal is to identify existing gaps of knowledge that the current study seeks to fill. The section presents organization growth and CSR under the following themes: education and leadership development and business expansion, financial literacy and access and business expansion, environmental conservation and business expansion and agricultural

support and business expansion. From the reviewed literature, a conceptual framework that guides the present study is presented.

Education and Leadership Development and Business Expansion

Leadership effectiveness has been a major issue in literature of world business, social issues, human resource management and development (Caligiuri & Tarique, 2012; Harteis, 2012). How to perform leadership duties efficiently in an increasingly tough global market is vital to international business and workforce management. Leadership is a key component of the modern organizations. Punnett, (2004) argued “Companies must accurately target their efforts to develop and recruit leaders who offer guidance in building true excellence in the most critical roles and competencies, which is eventually translated to revenue growth”. Aggarwa, (2011) observed that in order to cope with changes in demographics, technology, and globalization, specific job skill development for leadership, work ethic, and continuous learning is necessary. This is due to the fact that as demand for knowledge-based enterprises is on the rise, it is vital to enhance the success of workplace through learning and workforce development (Harteis, 2012). Additionally, leaders need to build their interpersonal skills to deal with conflicts and to develop individuals and groups in the workplace for them to acquire accelerated organization growth. Organizations have made this observation and are recently cashing in on the fad (Byrd, 2007). To enhance organizational competitiveness and performance, core values (e.g., performance excellence, innovation, social responsibility, worker involvement, and quality of work life) should be emphasized (Khana & Afzalb, 2011). All these cannot be achieved without the right leadership qualities within the organization obtained through training and education.

However, sourcing people with the right leadership qualities is not simple, and the best way is to train future leaders within the firm, where beneficiaries of its education project comprising of the most talented within the society are molded into future leaders and integrated into the organization. Afif Hossain and Bama Nazarius Neng (2011) observes that Grameen Bank sources its talent through education CSR project. This is unlike the organizations’ stand that the leadership and learning programs are more of CSR than institutional strategy. Education and leadership training projects should feed the society with skilled workforce from whom organizations source talent and which allows the firms to have access to a productive workforce that has the capability to boost growth. Though not empirically confirmed, the involvement of an organization in education and leadership CSR might influence the organization’s reputation in the employment market and hence lead to the ease in access of talent for the organization.

Financial Literacy and Access and Business Expansion

Financial literacy involves access to financial skills offering the ability to understand how money and economy work, how people earn or make money, and how they invest and use it to help themselves and others. One would expect that providing financial literacy services to a group would lead to access to economic growth and development for the people and no benefits to the organizations that offer the services. Amalric, et al., (2004) observed that the broadest view of the effectiveness of financial skills encompass a sense of responsible citizenship along with knowledge that creates a better society. Many advantages arise from improvement of financial skill and it follows that financial skills can result in economic growth.

According to King and Levine (1993), the main goal of financial literacy is to address challenge of low financial capabilities and equip people with the confidence to make “sound financial decisions, effectively manage financial services, and develop and work towards a tangible savings goal, as well as entrepreneurial programs” that increase the financial capabilities of people. Mandell (2004) defines financial literacy as “a guided increase in financial knowledge or skills and changes in financial behavior”. He claims that financial literacy provides the ability to “read, analyze, manage and communicate personal financial conditions that affect material wellbeing”. Financial literacy is therefore essential, and not just for investors, but for the average family trying to decide how to balance its budget, buy a home, fund the children education and ensure an income when the parents retire.

However, Agnew and Szykman (2005) showed that consumers with low income and low educational attainment tend to be the ones with low financial knowledge, which makes them not the most suitable customers to financial institutions. Given the high cost of carrying out these financial trainings, the firm might not be able to break even in relation to acquired customers and attached benefits and incurred costs. Moreover, Prete (2013) showed that a household's access to financial services is not based on levels of financial skill but on factors such as income levels, distance from banks, age, marital status, gender, household size, and level of education. With these factors unchanged, the financial institution might not benefit at all from the undertaking. Oseifuah (2010) on the other hand stated that more research is needed to verify in specific and practical terms the level and impact of financial literacy on organization growth of MSEs. He called for further research into the level and impact of financial literacy on organizations performance and development. Karlan and Valdivia (2010) did not find increase in financial literacy impacting business outcomes. However, Drexler, et al., (2010) did find that increase in financial literacy impact business outcomes leading to organization growth in the long run.

Organizations offering financial literacy and access services as a form of CSR can benefit from the undertakings. "This enhances their ability to be banked and at the same time allowing the financial institution to develop more income streams from the growing population, therefore boosting its capabilities of growth in the long run" (Bönte & Filiak, 2012). Wachira and Kihui (2012) observed that there is a high likelihood for beneficiaries of financial literacy skills to seek financial access through the firm offering these skills. With financial institutions offering these skills and access at the same time, the institution benefits from improvement in the number of customers, where their customer size grows. With the high levels of financial illiteracy in the rural areas, carrying out financial literacy and access to this part of the population would provide an organization with a chance of providing financial access to those unbanked in the population and also to enhance their customer base in the region.

Environmental Conservation and Business Expansion

Traditionally, environmental protection has been considered to be "in the public interest" and external to private life. Governments have assumed principal responsibility for assuring environmental management, and have focused on creating and preserving a safe environment. They have directed the private sector to adopt environmentally sound behavior through regulations, sanctions and occasionally, incentives. Moser and Miller, (2001) observed that when environmental problems have arisen, the public sector has generally borne the responsibility for mitigation of environmental damage. However, the roles of sectors have been changing, with the private sector becoming an active partner in environmental protection through CSR adoption.

Many governments and businesses are now realizing that environmental protection and economic growth are not always in conflict. Environmental sustainability is an integral part of a sustainable growth strategy. While protection of the environment and economic growth are often seen as competing aims, highlighting the financial benefits of increased eco-efficiency, Akpan (2006) observed that the natural environment is central to economic activity and growth, providing the resources we need to produce goods and services, and absorbing unwanted processing by-products in form of waste. Moser and Miller, (2001) observed that the current strength of the arguments for CSR programs are driving companies increasingly towards the adoption of socially and environmentally responsible strategies.

There has been much popular discussion of the role of "green investors" in driving societies to adopt or advocate for environmentally friendly practices (Baron, 2007). Investors allocate their wealth between savings, charitable donations, or shares of a socially responsible firm. If some investors prefer to make their social donations through investing in socially responsible companies (perhaps in order to avoid taxation of corporate profits), then CSR can increase the value of the firm by attracting these investors. Graff and Small (2005), shows that the value of the firm is less than it would be without CSR, but one way in which investors derive value from CSR is where its shares trade at a price above what they would fetch if they hadn't invested in CSR. Another way is where companies try to attract and retain the best employees by making environmental commitments that are aligned with these employees' environmental values.

Frank (2003) surveyed Cornell University graduates and found that many are willing to accept substantially lower salaries in firms engaged in socially responsible activities.

Dibb, et al., (2012) observed that most companies that are environmentally responsible eventually have enhanced brand image and reputation which generate strategically important goodwill and enhanced customer loyalty from a CSR perspective. Typically, a consumer is drawn to a company and a brand that has a good reputation for providing service and products and delivering value, as defined by the customer. However, Dibb, et al. (2012) failed to show how gained customer loyalty from CSR activities enhances organization growth. With many key natural resources and ecosystems services scarce or under pressure, achieving sustained growth require absolute decoupling of the production of goods and services from their environmental impacts. Akpan (2006) observed that policies that improve the efficiency with which businesses use resources, such as energy, water and materials, produce not just environmental benefits but also financial savings for businesses. Additionally, organizations that are committed to CSR have access to socially responsible investment (SRI), where investors take into account considerations such as a company's environmental and socially responsible activities. This study sought the link between organization growth and environmental undertakings of the organization.

Agricultural support and Business Expansion

Considering that agricultural growth has a bigger impact on poverty reduction than other sectors (WDR 2008), investments in agricultural production have the potential of reducing poverty in the developing countries. Decades of low investment in agriculture have led to stagnating productivity and production levels. An important area for public action is supporting the small scale farmers and exporter initiatives, especially in capacity building. Bodies such as the public and private sector have proved critical in sustaining competitiveness of agricultural industries, both through direct investments and capacity building, (Tilly, 2007). Organizations can therefore be able to acquire accelerated growth by adopting CSR in agricultural support. Wang, et al., (2009) observed that agricultural support has both direct and indirect benefits to the growth of organizations involved in the CSR projects. They observed that organizations directly benefit with direct marketing to the farmers, improved company image, better publicity, growth in customers and gains in profits gained from increase in business from the farmers. However, these views were made in a study that was meant to complement CSR undertakings in China and therefore there was vested interest of the researcher. This study hopes to confirm these views by quantifying these views.

Agriculture has been described as the backbone of the country in many economic circles. It is one of the highest contributors to GDP in Bangladesh. However, agricultural productivity has been dwindling in the recent past due to changing climatic conditions and a shift into other productive activities. This has seen the entrance of CSR offering organizations in the sector with the aim of improving productivity, enhancing food security, reducing the environmental impact of agricultural production, poverty reduction, mitigating effects of climate change, and supporting economic transformation (Tilly, 2007). Though these programs are supposed to benefit the society involved, there has been indication of instances where the organizations providing these CSR activities have benefited from the undertakings. Juma (2011) observed that agricultural support enhances productivity in agriculture raising farm incomes and reducing poverty of farming households, hence enhancing savings capacity which will be introduced into the economy which causes economic development and improvement in the operating environment of the organization, hence have an indirect impact on growth of the institution.

Study Gap

For the banking industry, the relationship between corporate social responsibility and business expansion has not been examined extensively at the international level, and the few existing studies offer conflicting evidence. For example, Chih et al. (2010) investigated a total of 520 financial firms in 34 countries over 2003- 2010 associated with financial performance in terms of return on assets, return on equity, net interest income, and noninterest income. The results showed that the out of the firms that are socially responsible, some had better earnings management only for a short

period others did not experience any earnings management. Some of the results were inconclusive. Differences in the results could be related to measurement issues, differences in sample as well as sample period. This study hopes to analyze Equity bank's social performance and its impact on the business expansion.

Kariuki (2013) studied the challenges facing the Safaricom Foundation in aligning CSR to corporate strategy, where the study found that the institution was involved in employee and product related activities as compared to their involvement in community and environmental activities where implementation of CSR activities in organization was largely done through employees than through other stakeholders. However, none of these studies looked at CSR in light of its effects on performance or organizational growth.

The relation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and business expansion has evoked much interest among researchers. While some studies reveal a positive relationship between the two constructs, some others indicate a negative relationship, and still others establish no relationship between the two constructs. Though a positive relationship between CSR and firm growth has prevailed in many studies, results still remain inconclusive. Such inconclusiveness creates knowledge gap on the actual CSR attributes that influence a firm's growth.

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